

DEIMOS' GS4EO OVER ENTICE: A COST-EFFECTIVE CLOUD-BASED SOLUTION TO DEPLOY AND OPERATE FLEXIBLE BIG EO DATA SYSTEMS WITH OPTIMIZED PERFORMANCE

José Julio Ramos[†] and Jonathan Becedas[‡]

Elecnor Deimos

[†] Deimos UK Ltd.

Building R103, Fermi Avenue – Harwell Oxford
Didcot, OX11 0QR, UK
Tel.: +44 (0) 1235 56 7173
e-mail: jose-julio.ramos@deimos-space.co.uk

[‡] Satellite Systems

Francia 9, Poligono Industrial la Nava
13500 Puertollano, Ciudad Real
Tel.: + 34 926 44 35 78
e-mail: jonathan.becedas@elecnor-deimos.es

ABSTRACT

Processing and distribution of big space data still presents a critical challenge: the treatment of massive and large-sized data obtained from Earth Observation satellite recordings. Remote sensing industries implement on-site conventional infrastructures to acquire, store, process and distribute the geo-information generated. However these solutions do not cover sudden changes in the demand of services and the access to the information presents large latencies. Cloud infrastructures are envisaged as a possible solution to improve EO systems dealing with large datasets, however the current technology still presents some limitations: i) the virtual machine images (VMIs) are not optimized being highly over-sized which impacts in the costs of using the infrastructure and in the dynamic resources provisioning; and ii) the deployment of Virtual Machines (VM) in cloud has large duration, normally between 10 and 20 minutes which directly affects to the flexibility and dynamic scalability of the system. Deimos' research focuses in the development of Future Internet technologies in order to improve Earth Observation (EO) services and to highly reduce the costs associated with on premises deployment. Within the ENTICE H2020 project, Deimos intends to implement a flexible, cost-effective Payload Data Ground Segment (PDGS) in a cloud computing infrastructure by reducing 60% the VMI size, 30% VMI delivery time, 25% deployment time, 25% VM cost and 25% VM storage.

Index Terms— *Earth Observation, Remote Sensing, Future Internet, Cloud Computing, Big Data, ENTICE.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Although the proven importance of EO in society, the access to the information obtained from satellites follows traditional and expensive paths to cover on demand services for different potential customers: conventional data centres

and conventional distribution of services. This presents several drawbacks: i) the cost of acquiring recent images of the Earth is very high, which limits the access of the general public, ii) clients cannot access directly neither fast to the information they need because this has to be processed and ad-hoc distributed, iii) the service is not flexible to be adapted to sudden changes in the demand.

Cloud computing is presented as a possible solution to improve common services and create new market opportunities because it is elastic, scalable and it works on demand through virtualization of resources [1].

Satellite and Earth Observation applications are then clear use cases for deployment on the cloud for the following reasons:

- The global nature of EO data, with ground stations and users geographically located all over the world, mandates to deploy a worldwide infrastructure connecting stakeholders.
- The massive size of EO data generated by today's sensors, in the order of daily Terabytes, suggests the use of a cost-effective procurement of the computer infrastructure for archive and processing.
- The amount of resources needed to optimally process and distribute EO data to the global user community is large.

Earth Observation systems are ideal use cases to be deployed on a cloud infrastructure with a dedicated middleware for automatic and intelligent provisioning and deployment to run EO applications.

2. BACKGROUND

In previous work of the research group, an Earth Observation system was successfully implemented in Future Internet cloud infrastructure: the GEO-Cloud project [2].

The GEO-Cloud project was an experiment in which a complete EO system was implemented in Fed4FIRE (<http://www.fed4fire.eu/>) [3]. A data centre was

specifically designed to be implemented as a distributed system, and a simulator of a satellite constellation was developed and implemented. Numerous users were emulated remotely accessing to the infrastructure. Promising results were obtained from that work [4]:

- Parallelization of processes to reduce the image processing time.
- Reduction of delivery time to end users.
- Possibility of having a distributed data centre on the World to facilitate the ingestion of images from a network of antennas.
- Externalization of infrastructure costs.
- On demand cost of computing resources

Then the system was implemented in a commercial infrastructure, in SoftLayer®, with the support of our IBM and Itera Process partners [5] with a successful increase in the computing performance among other improvements:

- Reduction of data transfers by using shared storage.
- Auto scaling
- Image processing time reduction
- 24/365 support
- Replication and download to local storage.
- Reconfiguration of instances on the fly.
- Security.

However, there are two major issues that can highly improve the applicability of cloud computing to EO applications:

- Storage in public cloud infrastructures is expensive, so effort in the optimization of virtual machines has to be done to reduce the high costs of implementing a whole mission, which have several years duration, in cloud.
- A major aspect is that the deployment of VMs is of several minutes, usually about 10 minutes [5]. For real time elasticity this is a major problem since the system cannot be reconfigured in real time. For example to scale down or scale up the distribution of products in function of the users' demand. This increases the costs of using the infrastructure and the latency to deliver the final products.

Within the ENTICE H2020 project (<http://www.entice-project.eu/>), it is expected the creation of a middleware that will optimize the size of VMs, will reduce the deployment of the virtual machines and will increase the performance of the whole system. In this work we introduce the use of ENTICE to increase the performance of the Earth Observation Payload Data Ground Segment which is being used to manage the data recorded by the high resolution satellite Deimos-2. It is intended that the commercial system will be included in the gs4EO suite as the Cloud Processing Station (CPS) component.

3. USE CASES

The CPS system will typically have three main trialling use cases iterating with different external actors:

- Use Case A. "Land Management" - Governments, planning offices and agricultural agencies need to characterize landscape and crops in vast rural regions. These users demand a multi-temporal product which allows analysing the land cover dynamics and detecting changes during a vast amount of time. The main objective is to optimize the archive of satellite recordings in order to facilitate reprocessing campaigns and time-series analysis.
- Use Case B. "Infrastructure monitoring" - During the construction or operations of major infrastructures in remote, hazardous areas such as high performance railway lines in the desert. These infrastructures would need constant monitoring to minimize the impact of the ambient conditions. The main objective is to optimize the processing of the satellite imagery to facilitate on-demand processing.
- Use Case C. "Disaster response" - Upon the event of a disaster, say an earthquake on a remote area, government and safety agencies would need to acquire, as soon as possible, images from the affected area before, during and after the event. Those images would be later demanded by a huge number of users from all around the world, either to manage emergency services and to assess the damages. The objective is to optimize the distribution of satellite imagery at a global scale by creating a Content Distribution Network.

4. OPTIMIZATION OBJECTIVES

Thus, to fulfil the objectives described in the Use Cases of section 3, the Cloud Processing Station (CPS) pilot case for ENTICE has to optimize a Space Data System deployed on cloud. Two main metrics are defined to validate the system: its overall data latency and system cost without any re-engineering activity.

- **Data latency** - Space Data Systems deployed on premises generates products after three generic steps which defines the overall system's data latency: processing, archiving and distribution. Each of these steps includes a data movement phase over a network (with latency depending on data quantity and server proximity) to present the data to the core functionality, respectively processing, archiving and distribution. A scalable deployment of the system on the cloud would include added activities to each general step dedicated to Virtual Machines management (provisioning, importing/exporting, spinning up and down, migration, destruction, etc.) which, while improving the system's

scalability, will impact negatively on the overall data latency. One of the ENTICE optimization objectives is to reduce the overall data latency by increasing its flexibility, minimizing the penalties on latency introduced by the VM management activities. Additionally, it also improves the core functionality performance.

- **System cost** - The main economic appeal of cloud computing consists of 'converting capital expenses to operating expenses' and paying for the use of utilities (resources in IaaS cloud model) reducing the risks of over- and under-provisioning a system [1]. Storage and computational resources like CPU architecture and memory directly affect the overall cost of a cloud deployment. ENTICE aims to minimise both needs by reducing the sizes of VMs, VM images and VM templates and the overall use of computational resources stripping down key functionality (processing, storage and distribution) of unnecessary dependencies, plus the time dedicated to VM management.

By applying ENTICE technology during the trialling of the distributed data centre proposed, we expect to reduce 60% the VMI size, 30% VMI delivery time, 25% deployment time, 25% VM storage and for instance at least a 25% VM of cost reduction in the use of cloud infrastructures.

5. ENTICE TECHNOLOGY

The development of the ENTICE middleware has the following main objectives:

- To simplify the creation of lightweight and highly optimised VM images tuned for functional descriptions of applications.
- To automatically decompose and distribute VM images based on multi-objective optimisation to meet application runtime requirements, performance, economic costs, storage size and QoS needs.
- To elastically auto-scale applications on Cloud resources based on their fluctuating load with optimised VM interoperability across Cloud infrastructures and without provider lock-in.

Those objectives are in line with the detected problems of current cloud technology detected in the GEO-Cloud project, and which are proposed to be solved with this work. The ENTICE middleware facilitates the implementation of the Cloud Processing Station system in cloud is done with the through functional descriptors. These functional descriptors define the system Service Level Agreement define at high and functional level the VMIs of the modules of the architecture and feed a Knowledge Base which highly contributes to optimize the VMIs. ENTICE analyses, synthesizes and optimizes the VMIs by automatically

removing unnecessary VM content like unused libraries or old log files or merging different VM templates stored in the system. ENTICE also provides a federated cloud as a testbed for trialling the use cases. Figure 1 depicts the high level architecture of the ENTICE environment.

Figure 1 Architecture of ENTICE technology. Source: <http://www.entice-project.eu/>

6. GS4EO CLOUD BASED IMPLEMENTATION WITH ENTICE

The GS4EO distributed architecture computed in cloud makes use of the ENTICE environment for its virtualization. The system is constituted by a GS Monitor which continuously pools over the different ground stations subscribed to the system, a Product Processors module which processes the raw data obtained from the satellite, an Archive and Catalogue module which stores and classifies the processed images and a module providing User Services. Figure 2 shows a scheme of the implementation concept with ENTICE.

Figure 2 Implementation concept of the gs4EO Cloud Processing Station with ENTICE

7. FURTHER DISCUSSIONS

One added effect of applying the ENTICE technology on a system is obtaining a process for automatic generation of micro-services [6]. The nature of the ENTICE optimization phase allows a “top-down” approach on system engineering, i.e., by gradually removing all non-essential features not included in a functional description. If the functional description includes only one task, this optimization would generate a single task-focused micro-service without having to re-engineer the complete software from “bottom-up” into smaller modules.

One further consideration on this project regards system scalability. The Use Cases for testing the ENTICE technology, i.e. Land Management, Infrastructure Monitoring and Disaster Response are designed for scaling the three main parts of the system (respectively Storage, Processing and Distribution) and having to response to variable data demand scenarios. Scaling the data supply side is currently limited to adjusting for sporadic changes on the data reception (failures in ground station antennas or satellites) or to well-known passing-by calendars as defined by satellite flight dynamics. However, there exists the possibility to include further unpredictable (or linked to user requirements) variations on the data acquisition side of the system by using virtual, swarm-like constellations of satellites like the Proba-3 mission concept [7], federation of satellite constellations or even virtual satellites providing access to internal resources to different customers in the same fashion as the “ground” IaaS model, a sort of cloud computing in space [8].

8. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of Earth Observation infrastructures proposed in this work contributes to optimize traditional EO data centres on premises with centralized storage and slow distribution of final products to convert the system in a flexible data centre based on scalability and flexibility of resources that optimizes the costs, improves the distribution of final products, provides on-demand services and facilitates the automation of the system while complying with a contracted level of service. The implementation approach with ENTICE facilitates the high level implementation and optimization of the resources by reducing the size of the VMIs, enhancing the overall system functionality by eliminating unnecessary processes and the deployment time of instances, which directly affects to the increase in the performance of the product processors and to the reduction of VM storage and costs in the use of cloud IaaS.

9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644179.

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